

Unveiling the Performance Metrics: An Experimental Study on Sectoral Mutual Funds

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Abstract: The present paper is based experimental analysis on the study of profitability and projected growth analysis of the sectoral fund in India in respect of bare risk and return. Sectorial funds are an avenue that is built with the aim to help investors capitalize on such opportunities. The best sector mutual funds invest in a portfolio of the top-performing businesses functioning in the same industry. The purpose of this paper is to examine profitability analysis, among the 10 select sectoral funds its average profit for last 10 years, compounded annual growth rate and projected growth rate for future years comparing the return and risk assessment of top selected sectorial mutual funds with the help of financial ratios and linear trends. This paper may provide useful insights and guidance for the present and prospective investors of mutual fund investment in India.

Index Terms sectorial mutual funds, profitability performance, risk assessment, compounded annual growth rate. Projected growth rate

I. INTRODUCTION

Mutual funds are managed by sound financial professionals known as fund managers, who have the expertise in analysing and managing investments. The funds collected from investors in mutual funds are invested by the fund managers in different financial assets such as stocks, bonds, and other assets, as defined by the fund's investment objective. The Indian economy consists of different sectors such as technology, banking, pharma, natural resources, and more. Some of these sectors might perform outstandingly well in the medium to long term. Sectorial funds are an avenue that is built with the aim to help investors capitalize on such opportunities. All sectors don't move in tandem with the economy. Sectors are cyclical in nature. They have some good ones as well as some bad ones. So, based on your research and analysis, if you can catch the right cycle, you have a chance of earning exceptional returns by investing in sectorial funds. Sectorial funds are an avenue that is built with the aim to help investors capitalize on such

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Sectorial funds represent an investment avenue designed to enable investors to leverage opportunities within specific industries. The premier sector mutual funds typically comprise portfolios of high-performing businesses operating within the same industry. The primary objective of this research is to scrutinize the profitability analysis of ten chosen sectorial funds over the past decade, including their average profit, compounded annual growth rate (CAGR), and projected growth rate for forthcoming years. The study will entail a comparative assessment of return and risk among the top-selected sectorial mutual funds, employing financial ratios and linear trends. Ultimately, this paper aims to furnish valuable insights and guidance for both current and prospective mutual fund investors in India.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is essential since it familiarizes the researcher with concepts and conclusions already evolved by earlier analysis. It also enables the here, researcher to find out the scope of study and frame suitable objectives for the proposed evaluation. Since the proposal of the study is to measure the selected sectorial mutual funds in India. It also includes the opinions expressed by various authors in leading articles, journals and books.

1. Jacob and Kattookaran (2014) The research help in selection of best mutual fund schemes in the terms of risk and return. Reliance Liquid Cash Fund is found to generate the highest return for each unit of risk taken according to Sharpe ratio. In terms of market risk (Beta), also the Reliance Liquid Cash Flow shows the lowest Beta. However, UTI Floating Fund ST (Reg) shows the lowest risk for systematic and unsystematic risk. Further, the researchers suggested for awareness spreading and investor-friendly program, reduction of load fees and increase in ceiling limit of foreign investment in mutual fund

2. Jack L. Treynor (1965) this study suggested a new measure of mutual fund performance evaluation. This measure is different from those used previously by incorporating the volatility of a fund's return in a simple yet meaningful manner.

3. A study by El-khoury & Ritab (1993) In this study examine the risk-return relationship of mutual funds by taking into consideration those mutual funds, which are registered in the Amman stock exchange. They use CAPM version of market model (SLM). Their study report

4. Lewellen and Lease' (1975) This study analysed the individual investor's risk aversion and investment portfolio composition and identified that age and risk-taking propensities were inversely related with major shifts taking place at the age of 55 and beyond.

5. Kavita and Pasricha (2017) During the study period 2000 – 2015, it has been observed that macroeconomics variables like consumer price index, gross domestic savings, exchange rate, growth rate, interest rate and nifty returns do not have considerable influence in mutual fund flow. The paper says that fund flow is affected by the fund's own limitations and past performance.

4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Main objectives of this paper are as follows

- To study the overview of sectorial mutual funds in India.
- To analyses and forecast the trend profits of select sectorial mutual funds.
- To compare the sectorial mutual funds' profit performance among top select funds in India.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

H01: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Rural and Consumption Fund issued in India.

H02: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Franklin Build India Fund issued in India.

H03: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund issued in India.

H04: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at IDFC Infrastructure Fund issued in India.

H05: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund issued in India.

H06: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund issued in India.

H07: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at SBI Magnum COMMA Fund issued in India.

H08: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund issued in India.

H09: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund issued in India.

H10: Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Nippon India Power and Infra Fund issued in India.

6. METHODOLOGY

The design of the present study is an analytical in nature and covers the top performed 10 sectorial mutual funds for period of 10 years from 2013 to 2023. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfil our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the concerned official of each sector of selected mutual funds and mutual funds experts through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the mutual funds.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the SEBI Reports are also used to supplement the secondary data.

7. TOOLS USED FOR STUDY ANALYSIS

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as statistical descriptions, correlation analysis least square trend and t-test is used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

8. SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF STUDY:

The below mentioned are the constraints under which studies are carried out

- a. The collection of data analysis is restricted to Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India only.
- b. The study is limited by time constraints.
- c. The study is based mainly on secondary data collected from websites of NSE, BSE and Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India.

9. ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

Table No. 1
1. Statement of Sundaram Rural and Consumption Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-0.6	-	2023	20.16+(-0.94) (11) = 9.82
2015	47.4	-8000	2024	20.16+(-0.94) (12) = 8.88
2016	6.3	-86.70	2025	20.16+(-0.94) (13) = 7.94
2017	21.1	234.92	2026	20.16+(-0.94) (14) = 7
2018	38.7	83.41	-	-
2019	-7.8	-120.15	-	-
2020	2.7	-134.61	-	-
2021	13.5	400	-	-
2022	19.3	42.96	-	-
2023	9.3	-51.81	-	-
Average	14.99	-847.99	-	-
Maximum	47.4	400	-	-
Minimum	-7.8	-8000	-	-
CAGR (%)	11.9	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-1

Inference: Table 1 Presented that the returns performance of Sundaram Rural and Consumption Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 47.4 percent was seen in the year 2015 and minimum return was -7.8 percent made in the years 2019. Average return for the past 10 years is 14.99 percent and its CAGR is 11.9 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 400 percent is seen in the year 2021 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -8,000 percent is noticed in the years 2015 and average growth rate is -847.99 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing trend between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 9.82 percent seen in the 2024 percent and 7.00 percent made in the years 2027. This fund is not suggestible for future four years for investment.

Table No. 2
2. Statement of Franklin Build India Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	6.1	-	2023	31.1+(-1.81) (11) = 11.19
2015	93.8	1437.70	2024	31.1+(-1.81) (12) = 9.38
2016	2.1	-97.76	2025	31.1+(-1.81) (13) = 7.57
2017	8.4	300	2026	31.1+(-1.81) (14) = 5.76
2018	43.3	415.47	-	-
2019	-10.7	-124.71	-	-
2020	6	-156.07	-	-
2021	5.4	-10	-	-
2022	45.9	750	-	-
2023	11.2	-75.59	-	-
Average	21.15	271.00	-	-
Maximum	93.8	1437.70	-	-
Minimum	-10.7	-156.07	-	-
CAGR (%)	16.3	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure- 2

Inference: Table-2 Presented that the returns performance of Franklin Build India Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 93.8 percent was seen in the year 2015 and minimum return was -10.7 percent noticed in the years 2018. Average return for the past 10 years is 21.15 percent and its CAGR is 16.3 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 1437.70 percent is seen in the year 2015 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -156.07 percent is noticed in the years 2019 and average growth rate is -271 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing trend between year 2024 to year 2026. Projected return of this fund is 11.19 percent seen in the year 2024 percent and 5.76 percent made in the years 2027. This fund is not suggestible for future four years for investment.

Table No. 3
3. Statement of DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-5.7	-	2023	17.17+0.02 (11) = 17.99
2015	46.8	-921.05	2024	17.17+0.02 (12) = 18.01
2016	-1.7	-103.63	2025	17.17+0.02 (13) = 18.03
2017	43.1	-2635.29	2026	17.17+0.02 (14) = 18.05
2018	43.1	0	-	-
2019	-15.3	-135.49	-	-
2020	4.4	-128.75	-	-
2021	11.5	161.36	-	-
2022	42.8	272.17	-	-
2023	9.8	-77.10	-	-
Average	17.88	-396.42	-	-
Maximum	46.8	272.17	-	-
Minimum	-15.3	-2635.29	-	-
CAGR (%)	12.4	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-3

Inference: Table-3 Presented that the returns performance of DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 46.8 percent was seen in the year 2015 and minimum return was -15.3 percent noticed in the years 2018. Average return for the past 10 years is 17.88 percent and its CAGR is 12.4 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 272.17 percent is seen in the year 2022 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -2635.29 percent is noticed in the years 2017 and average growth rate is -396 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been increasing trend between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 17.99 percent seen in the year 2023 percent and 18.05 percent made in the years 2027. This DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund is recommended for future four years for investment.

Table No. 4

Statement of IDFC Infrastructure Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-10.8	-	2023	9.48+0.88(11) = 19.16
2015	43.2	-500	2024	9.48+0.88(12) = 18.78
2016	-0.2	-100.46	2025	9.48+0.88(13) = 17.9
2017	10.7	-5450	2026	9.48+0.88(14) = 17.02
2018	58.7	448.59	-	-
2019	-25.9	-144.12	-	-
2020	-5.3	-79.54	-	-
2021	6.3	-218.86	-	-
2022	64.8	928.57	-	-
2023	1.7	-97.37	-	-
Average	14.32	-579.24	-	-
Maximum	64.8	928.57	-	-
Minimum	-25.9	-5450	-	-
CAGR (%)	9.1	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-4

Inference: Table-4 Presented that the returns performance of IDFC Infrastructure Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 64.8 percent was seen in the year 2022 and minimum return was -25.9 percent noticed in the years 2018. Average return for the past 10 years is 14.32 percent and its CAGR is 9.1 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 928.57 percent is seen in the year 2022 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -5450 percent is noticed in the years 2017 and average growth rate is -579.24 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been increasing trend between year 2023 to year 2026. Projected return of this fund is 19.16 percent seen in the year 2024 percent and 17.02 percent made in the years 2027. This IDFC Infrastructure Fund is recommended for future four years for investment.

Table No. 5

Statement of Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-6.8	-	2023	22.97+(-1.2) (11) = 9.77
2015	65.8	-1067.64	2024	22.97+(-1.2) (12) = 8.57
2016	-0.5	-100.75	2025	22.97+(-1.2) (13) = 7.37
2017	15.7	-3240	2026	22.97+(-1.2) (14) = 6.17
2018	47.6	203.18	-	-
2019	-2.4	-105.04	-	-
2020	14.9	-720.83	-	-
2021	1.1	-92.61	-	-
2022	16.8	1427.27	-	-
2023	11.5	-31.54	-	-
Average	16.37	-414.22	-	-
Maximum	65.8	1427.27	-	-
Minimum	-6.8	-3240	-	-
CAGR (%)	17.1	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-5

Inference: Table-5 Presented that the returns performance of Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 65.8 percent was seen in the year 2015 and minimum return was -6.8 percent noticed in the years 2013. Average return for the past 10 years is 11.5 percent and its CAGR is 17.1 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 1427.27 percent is seen in the year 2022 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -3240 percent is noticed in the years 2017 and average growth rate is -31.54 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 9.77 percent seen in the year 2024 percent and 6.17 percent made in the years 2027. This Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund is not suggested for future four years for investment.

Table No. 6

1. Statement of Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-6.7	-	2023	19.63+(-14) (11) = 18.09
2015	80.7	-1304.47	2024	19.63+(-14) (12) = 17.95
2016	-0.2	-100.24	2025	19.63+(-14) (13) = 17.81
2017	9.2	-4700	2026	19.63+(-14) (14) = 17.67
2018	45.3	392.39	-	-
2019	-19.6	-143.26	-	-
2020	3.6	-118.36	-	-
2021	3.4	-5.55	-	-
2022	57.3	1585.29	-	-
2023	15.6	-72.77	-	-
Average	18.86	-496.33	-	-
Maximum	80.7	1585.29	-	-
Minimum	-19.6	-4700	-	-
CAGR (%)	10	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-6

Inference: Table-6 Presented that the returns performance of Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 80.7 percent was seen in the year 2015 and minimum return was -19.6 percent noticed in the years 2019. Average return for the past 10 years is 18.86 percent and its CAGR is 10 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 1585.24 percent is seen in the year 2022 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -4700 percent is noticed in the years 2017 and average growth rate is -496.33 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 18.09 percent seen in the year 2023 percent and 17.67 percent made in the years 2027. This Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund is suggested for future four years for investment.

Table No. 7
Statement of SBI Magnum COMMA Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-13.7	-	2023	7.46+1.29 (11) = 21.65
2015	31.5	-329.92	2024	7.46+1.29 (12) = 22.94
2016	-6.1	-119.36	2025	7.46+1.29 (13) = 24.23
2017	32.3	-629.50	2026	7.46+1.29 (14) = 25.52
2018	39.2	21.36	-	-
2019	-18.7	-147.70	-	-
2020	11.8	-163.10	-	-
2021	23.9	102.54	-	-
2022	52	117.57	-	-
2023	-6.6	-112.69	-	-
Average	14.56	-140.09	-	-
Maximum	52	117.57	-	-
Minimum	-18.7	-629.50	-	-
CAGR (%)	11.5	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-7

Inference: Table-7 Presented that the returns performance of SBI Magnum COMMA Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 52 percent was seen in the year 2022 and minimum return was -18.7 percent noticed in the years 2019. Average return for the past 10 years is 14.56 percent and its CAGR is 11.5 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 117.57 percent is seen in the year 2022 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -629.50 percent is noticed in the years 2017 and average growth rate is -140.09 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 21.65 percent seen in the year 2023 percent and 25.52 percent made in the years 2027. This SBI Magnum COMMA Fund is suggested for future four years for investment.

Table No. 8
8. Statement of SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	5.3	-	2023	13.15+0.49 (11) = 18.54
2015	30.9	483.02	2024	13.15+0.49 (12) = 19.03
2016	5.3	-82.85	2025	13.15+0.49 (13) = 19.52
2017	2.4	-54.72	2026	13.15+0.49 (14) = 20.01
2018	53.1	2112.5	-	-
2019	-2	-103.76	-	-
2020	0.1	-105	-	-
2021	13.9	13800	-	-
2022	35.6	156.11	-	-
2023	13.9	-60.95	-	-
Average	15.85	1793.81	-	-
Maximum	53.1	13800	-	-
Minimum	-2	-105	-	-
CAGR (%)	15.5	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-8

Inference: Table-8 Presented that the returns performance of SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 53.1 percent was seen in the year 2018 and minimum return was -2.00 percent noticed in the years 2019. Average return for the past 10 years is 15.85 percent and its CAGR is 15.5 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 13800 percent is seen in the year 2021 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -105 percent is noticed in the years 2019 and average growth rate is 1793.81 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between years 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 18.54 percent seen in the year 2023 percent and 20.01 percent made in the years 2027. This SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund is recommended for future four years for investment.

Table No. 9
9. Statement of Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	9.9	-	2023	19.66+(-0.46) (11) = 14.6
2015	42.7	331.31	2024	19.66+(-0.46) (12) = 14.14
2016	3.8	-91.10	2025	19.66+(-0.46) (13) = 13.68
2017	2	-47.36	2026	19.66+(-0.46) (14) = 13.22
2018	51	2450	-	-
2019	1.9	-96.27	-	-
2020	8.6	352.63	-	-
2021	11.2	30.23	-	-
2022	33	194.64	-	-
2023	7.2	-78.18	-	-
Average	17.13	338.43	-	-
Maximum	51	2450	-	-
Minimum	1.9	-96.27	-	-
CAGR (%)	16.8	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-9

Inference: Table-9 Presented that the returns performance of Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 51 percent was seen in the year 2018 and minimum return was 1.9 percent noticed in the years 2019. Average return for the past 10 years is 17.13 percent and its CAGR is 16.8percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 2450 percent is seen in the year 2018 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -96.27 percent is noticed in the years 2018 and average growth rate is 338.43 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 14.6 percent seen in the year 2024 percent and 13.22 percent made in the years 2027. This Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund is not recommended for future four years for investment.

Table No. 10
Statement of Nippon India Power and Infra Fund

Year	Return (%)	Growth (%)	Year	Trend Return
2014	-14.6	-	2023	9.21+0.96 (11) = 19.77
2015	50.8	-447.94	2024	9.21+0.96 (12) = 20.73
2016	0.3	-99.41	2025	9.21+0.96 (13) = 21.69
2017	0.1	-66.66	2026	9.21+0.96 (14) = 22.65
2018	61.7	61600	-	-
2019	-21.1	-134.19	-	-
2020	-2.9	-86.25	-	-
2021	10.8	-472.41	-	-
2022	48.9	352.77	-	-
2023	10.9	-77.71	-	-
Average	14.49	6729.79	-	-
Maximum	61.7	61600	-	-
Minimum	-21.1	-472.41	-	-
CAGR (%)	17	-	-	-

Source: Association of mutual funds and Money control in India

Figure-10

Inference: Table-10 Presented that the returns performance of Nippon India Power and Infra Fund for the past 10 years is as follows; High return 61.7 percent was seen in the year 2018 and minimum return was -21.1 percent noticed in the years 2018. Average return for the past 10 years is 14.49 percent and its CAGR is 17 percent.

Growth rate of return of this fund for the last 10 years maximum positive growth rate is 61600 percent is seen in the year 2018 and minimum negative growth rate of return is -472.41 percent is noticed in the years 2021 and average growth rate is 6729.79 percent. Projected growth rate of this fund has been decreasing movement between year 2024 to year 2027. Projected return of this fund is 19.77 percent seen in the year 2023 percent and 22.65 percent made in the years 2027. This Nippon India Power and Infra Fund is recommended for future four years for investment.

10. TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS:

(Sectorial performance among top ten selected mutual funds in India)

In this section, hypotheses relating to 10 selected sectors consisting of 1. Rural and Consumption Fund 2. Franklin Build India Fund 3. DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund 4. IDFC Infrastructure Fund 5. Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund 6. Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund 7. SBI Magnum COMMA Fund 8. SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund 9. Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund 10. Nippon India Power and Infra Fund, these sub hypotheses are specified in chapter (i) are tested using the correlation co-efficient of sectorial performance among top ten selected mutual funds in India to know the uniqueness of among the variables, and the t-test used the hypothesis for the result. The hypothesis is re-stated as follows:

Table- 11
Testing of Hypotheses Concerning to Sectorial performance among top ten selected mutual funds in India
T- TEST ANALYSIS

Specific Factor	Sub Hypothesis	t- Test	Critical Value (t_{α})	P-Value	Hypothesis Result
H ₀₁	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Rural and Consumption Fund issued in India.	//2.30/	2.365	0.0550	Accepted
H ₀₂	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Franklin Build India Fund issued in India.	//2.57//	2.262	0.0300	Rejected
H ₀₃	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund issued in India.	//2.44//	2.447	0.0500	Accepted
H ₀₄	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at IDFC Infrastructure Fund issued in India.	//1.74//	2.447	0.0132	Accepted
H ₀₅	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund issued in India.	//1.09//	4.308	0.3900	Accepted
H ₀₆	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund issued in India.	//2.54//	2.365	0.0390	Rejected
H ₀₇	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at SBI Magnum COMMA Fund issued in India.	//2.09//	2.447	0.0820	Accepted
H ₀₈	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund issued in India.	//1.82//	2.228	0.0980	Accepted
H ₀₉	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund issued in India.	//2.69//	2.365	0.0310	Rejected
H ₁₀	Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance at Nippon India Power and Infra Fund issued in India.	//2.63//	2.262	0.0270	Rejected

* Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$.

Source: Computed

Table No.11 The present table Reveals that the t-test of Sectorial performance among top ten selected mutual funds in India. It can be seen that all these 10 select sectors mutual. All these funds, which are tested its 10 hypotheses with t-test, the output result, it is clear that out of ten sector six sector have Sector allocation of mutual funds is different performance. Which are Rural and Consumption Fund, DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund, IDFC Infrastructure Fund, Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund, SBI Magnum COMMA Fund and SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund. All these six funds hypotheses are accepted, where, computed values less than computed t- critical value at 5% level of significance. Whereas, remain four funds, which are Franklin Build India Fund. Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund, Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund and Nippon India Power and Infra Fund, these funds hypotheses are rejected, where calculate t-value higher than the t-critical value at 5 % level of significance.

Therefore, it is observed that Rural and Consumption Fund, DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund, IDFC Infrastructure Fund, Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund, SBI Magnum COMMA Fund and SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund; different performance seen at Sector allocation of mutual funds and other four funds; Franklin Build India Fund. Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund, Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund and Nippon India Power and Infra Fund; no different performance seen at Sector allocation of mutual funds for last 10 years in Indian Mutual Funds industry.

11. CONCLUSION

Sector funds have the potential of delivering extremely high returns on investment if the sector that one chooses starts to perform well. Sector mutual fund investors can invest during such a downward trend so they can gain immensely when the sector performs well eventually. Investors must possess proper knowledge regarding a particular sector and its overall performance before investing in the same. Without such an in-depth understanding, an investor may misread current market trends, ultimately leading to losses. This can dilute investor exposure to a sector and shall not provide the yield as expected by the investor. Light of above analysis, these are the main observations:

- Out of 10 select sectorial mutual funds projected trend profits have been observed in favour of four funds coming four years. The prospective funds are DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund, SBI Magnum COMMA Fund, SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund and Nippon India Power and Infra Fund.
- It is observed that 15 percent above Compound Annual Growth Rate is good at Franklin Build India Fund, Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund, Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund, SBI Consumption Opportunities Fund, Mirae Asset Great Consumer Fund and Nippon India Power and Infra Fund during the study period.
- It is noticed that funds, Rural and Consumption Fund, DSP Black Rock Natural Resources and New Energy Fund, IDFC Infrastructure Fund, Aditya Birla Sun Life Banking and Financial Services Fund, SBI Magnum COMMA Fund and SBI Consumption Opportunities, among these seven funds have different financial and operational performance seen out of select Sector allocation of mutual funds in India.
- Sectorial mutual funds' performance for the past 10 years, It is noticed that all 10 select sectorial mutual funds have above 10 percent average profits during the study period.
- It is observed that up to 20 percent average profits realized in favour of Franklin Build India Mutual Fund during last 10 years.

To conclude, all the select sectorial funds, it is suggested that better to allocate possible extent of investment its funds into pharm sector, aviation sector, food processing and health care sector. The best sector mutual funds is requiring a significant period to reach their true potential. These sector fund options can help individuals achieve financial milestones for mutual funds investment.

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